

EOSC - Let's get practical! Vol. 1

Interview with Inge van Nieuwerburgh and Paula Oset (Ghent University) about the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue

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Marie

Hello and welcome to today's episode of Stories of Data - the Open Science Talk.

I am Marie and together with my colleague Andreas I have today the honor to welcome two very special guests: Inge and Paula from Ghent University. They are experts in research data management and will present their RDM training and support catalogue - a tool they developed within the EOSC-Pillar project.

Andreas

Perhaps the easiest thing to begin with would be a little bit of an introduction, so if you would like to introduce yourselves?

Inge

Ok, I'm Inge van Nieuwerburgh, I work in the Open Science team of Ghent University Library, also known as the book tower, now in our team in our university library we have the credo to facilitate Open Knowledge Creation, so what we do, we support our researchers to create knowledge - so we don't do research ourselves but we support researchers. And projects like EOSC-Pillar really fit into that purpose because we want to work with other colleagues to achieve that.

Paula

My name is Paula Oset, I work also with Inge at the Open Science Team at Ghent University but I am part of the data steward team. [...]

So my work is also related to or I do also support researchers in matters of research data management and all the different obligations around data management.

Marie

How did your story with EOSC-Pillar begin?

Inge

We support Open Science quite well in the University Library. So, working together with peers in all of Europe and align our activities is something we really like. And this is something that we do in EOSC Pillar as well. This project also supports collaboration between people involved in training, giving training to researchers, training coordinators. This has been an important pillar throughout the work of Open Science over the last few years, this collab with peers and make sure to become better professionals to

support our researchers.

Andreas

Thank you - then let's get practical now and talk about the tool that you developed...How would you describe what the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue is?

Paula

I think in a nutshell, it's a place where you can just find RDM training and support material, so if you are planning to give some training or you need to find a way to support a researcher with a specific question, you can go there and try to find if there is already existing material you can reuse. So the idea is to facilitate reuse of the already existing wealth of training and research support material that is out there in a central point or in a central place. Because there is already so much, but it's a little bit scattered. So this is the central point where you can find all of these materials.

Andreas

And why do you build up the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue?

Paula

So we started as a new team two years ago, it's kind of a new profession so we were looking at the Netherlands and the UK because they had a bit more experience in setting up RDM support. And we found that there was a lot of nice things out there, like slides of training courses or other material that was really good and that we could reuse.

But as I said its very scattered, so this was the underlying idea behind the catalogue, that it would be nice if there's a central point where you can look for all these materials, especially as a new team starting in a new job.

Marie

Thank you. Inge, regarding the catalogue, what are your goals?

Inge

Well, as said before, it's about collaboration, we want to collaborate with our peers, we each have a lot of work to do and its very good if we can learn from each other and if we can reuse material that we have all made. Open Science is about reuse and we have to do the same thing in training of course, so why not collaborate together and reuse what we have made within our own communities.

It's also part of a mutual learning experience, how can people learn from each other. It's quite an evolving field, there's new people coming in all the time, new people that have to learn what's going on and it's sometimes quite a steep learning curve. But on the other hand, a lot of people involved quite some time in training materials. They can learn from the fresh views of new people coming in.

The catalogue will also increase uptake, so the material is not hidden anymore. The more we promote the catalogue and our community knows about it, the uptake will increase and it's better for everyone if we can make our material better by sharing and reusing it. So it really facilitates RDM practices.

Paula

The final goal of the catalogue is to make material available that supports the implementation of good practices in RDM - so how researchers should perform research or incorporate data management as a part of their research, so that research becomes more transparent. As Inge said, it's a pillar of open science, transparency, the quality of science is increased. The final goal in the end is to increase the skills of researchers when it comes to research data management, so that they can implement these best practices.

Andreas

Alright, thank you. Who are the users that you're thinking of?

Paula

This is indeed one of the metadata fields of the catalogue, the target users and in principle this can be useful for anybody working on RDM support or open science support, so people like data stewards, or librarians, research officers, or any person that has a role in supporting researchers with any of the RDM requirements would benefit from it, because they find the already available and ready to use training material. But maybe also other roles like ethics officers because there is also material related to ethics, or GDPR requirements. And researchers themselves can benefit because some of the material can be useful to gain skills as a data steward, but these skills in the end should also be present with researchers. They are also target users of the catalogue.

Inge

Indeed, in the end, the researchers should get acquainted with open science skills, so we want to support researchers in their work.

Andreas

What are you proud of?

Paula

I would say that when you develop something with a goal in mind, you would hope that that goal will be achieved in the end. We have had quite positive feedback on our training and demonstration sessions. People who didn't know about the catalogue seemed to find it useful. So the fact that the catalogue serves the purpose it was meant for is very satisfying.

Andreas

And contrasting with that perhaps, what has been challenging?

Paula

There have been a few challenges along the way. So first, there is this issue around metadata standards, so trying to find an agreement on a standard way in which we can describe the content of the catalogue,

so the metadata schema. That is a still evolving, and recently, we have been involved with other projects such as EOSC Future to try to find an agreement on how we all describe the training material. That's a challenge, because there is no consensus yet, but we are getting there.

Another challenge is to judge what should go on the catalogue and what should not, so evaluating the quality and usefulness of the training material. That's difficult, especially when the material is very discipline-specific. You don't always have the appropriate knowledge to judge whether something is good enough for a specific field.

Marie

What are your plans for the near future?

Paula

Expanding our user base, but also including more discipline-specific resources and to promote the uptake within these discipline-specific communities. For that we are collaborating with partners in the project who run a series of discipline-specific use cases to see how we can engage with them and get more domain-specific content in the catalogue. We have less discipline-specific content than generic content at the moment.

Inge

We also want to keep on working with other training coordinators. There is this OpenAIRE community of practice of training coordinators, they meet every month. With that group, we had a workshop in the Open Science FAIR on training and support catalogues, discussing the challenges that we face. And it was with initiatives like the ELIXIR training portal TeSS, DARIAH campus and Social Sciences and Humanities Training Discovery Toolkit, where we work together with people from SSHOC. It gives you energy to see how we can work on those challenges together and work together within this community of practice. And we want to continue that to make our catalogue better on the one hand, and on the other hand to agree on certain standards and procedures within our catalogues to increase the quality. And that is again very important for the uptake and usefulness.

Andreas

If you could tell people one thing about either your field or your project, what would it be?

Inge

From the field I would say that transparency works! Opening up your research works. We have seen it throughout the pandemic, how important it was to share research findings and data, to enhance your own and other's work. We have seen that open science practices drive excellent science. That's really something that we would like to stress: Often, researchers think of open science practices as yet another thing they have to do, as a burden. But it has been shown that it really pays off and that you can do really good things by opening up your research and managing research data in a precise way.

Marie, Andreas

Very good answers. Thank you so much for your time. I think this will conclude our time together.

Marie,

So thank you very much for taking time.

Inge, Paula

You're welcome, no problem.

Andreas

Have a lovely day, take care and thank you again.

Inge, Paula

Bye, thank you.

Marie

Well, this has definitely been very informative, and it shines a spotlight on a lot of work done in an area that is always of great relevance, underpinning and enabling better research for all. Data accessibility, its management, its analysis, those are all key skills across all scientific disciplines.

Andreas

What I find very interesting is how the RDM training and support catalogue fills a similar niche to a toolkit developed as a part of SSHOC.

Marie

Oh? How so?

Andreas

One of the tools developed as a part of SSHOC is the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit, or toolkit for short. Similarly to the catalogue, it's an inventory of various learning and training materials that trainers of different disciplines in the Social Sciences and Humanities can use to find materials for reuse in their own training activities. It is still a work in progress, but it currently already contains more than 180 items from 78 different sources, and a number of links to a variety of materials on topics including Open Science, Research Data Management, and didactics, but also specific topics that are relevant to multiple disciplines, like text encoding and spatial data.

Marie

Interesting! I hope we'll get to explore this in more detail!

Andreas

That's the idea! Over the course of the next episodes, we'll further discuss a number of other toolsets designed to assist researchers across multiple fields, as well as their applications. But until then, as always - take care, stay safe, and stay curious!